

**USING THE KLISTER METHOD IN TEACHING THE KINEMATICS
DEPARTMENT OF THEORETICAL MECHANICS**

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Abstract. The article talks about the possibility of using the klyster method, which is one of the interactive methods for training students, in the science of theoretical mechanics.

Keywords. Theoretical mechanics, statics, kinematics, dynamics, law of motion, trajectory, velocity, acceleration, hodograph, projections, curvilinear motion, accelerating motion, decelerating motion.

In the last five years, great positive changes have been made in the field of education - the number of institutes has increased, the number of admission quotas has increased, the funding of the education system has improved, existing buildings have been overhauled, new ones have been built, and training has been improved. The curriculum has been improved. The task of improving the quality of education was given to the professors and teachers of the institute. The most optimal way to increase the effectiveness of education in modern conditions is to organize lessons using interactive methods. Appropriate and purposeful use of interactive methods in the educational process guarantees the realization of high pedagogical goals. The use of modern pedagogical and informational teaching technologies in the educational process not only increases the teacher's qualifications but also allows him to take a systematic approach to teaching the subject, taking into account the individual characteristics of students. Through these requirements, the student learns to plan and systematize the acquired

knowledge, learns the ability to work in a team, and manage a team. These factors are especially valued in the modern labor market.

The Kalaster method is one of the most effective ways to improve the quality of education by increasing demonstration in the teaching process. The interactive cluster method has the potential to be demonstrative, effective, and of great benefit in solving specific problems in all three parts of theoretical mechanics, both during lectures and during practical training. In the department of statics, the method can be applied to the following topics - equilibrium conditions of solid bodies, the center of gravity of a solid body, various force systems, and moments of force. And in the section of kinematics - mechanical movement, speed, acceleration, types of movement, expressions of complex movement of a point. In the department of dynamics, it is used for these topics - differential equations of motion, rectilinear vibration of a material point, momentum, kinetic energy, moments of inertia, etc.

Here is an example of using the cluster method. Spreading the word theoretical mechanics to a cluster. This word is first divided into 3 components, which in turn are further divided into components and so on. You can give the steps to create a cluster information map. The task is to gather the components around some central factor to center and define the essence of the whole structure. In the example above, the phrase "Theoretical Mechanics" is clustered; this cluster is interesting in that it can be further expanded by subdividing the components further. Cognitive thinking expands the process of the student's understanding of the relationship between all the components of this phrase and their constituents and acquires connections between the main words and phrases related to the topic.

The important aspect of the cluster method is that within the scope of the subject being studied, students will have the opportunity to first divide one topic of the subject, then one section, and finally the whole subject into its components, determine the connections between them, distinguish them from each other, and compare them. As a result, students' imagination and understanding will increase.

Below we present a description of the cluster created on the topic of "Point kinematics" of theoretical mechanics. In the process of creating a cluster, this phrase is first divided into constituents (law of motion, radius vector, trajectory), then each of them is divided into constituents, etc. The cluster is shown below.

It is also possible to use the cluster method to determine the knowledge gained by students on mid-term assessment or to evaluate the knowledge acquired in the lesson.

For this purpose, the teacher prepares, reproduces and distributes the material to the students on cluster formation based on the words suitable for the subject material being taught. Above is a cluster task prepared on the topic of the power system. Students study the topic and complete the cluster using their acquired knowledge. The teacher evaluates the created cluster.

In conclusion, the use of the cluster method in lectures and practical classes of theoretical mechanics has a positive effect on students' mastery of the subject. This situation leads to an increase in their knowledge.

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